

Bhattacharya alkali test of rice

dish, and 2) that the number of grains per dish should be such as to leave a minimum mean space of 5–6 cm²/grain. Once these conditions are met (it is immaterial if the limits are slightly exceeded), the volume of alkali per grain can be ignored. We have been using reference method II in our routine work. However, alternative VIII might be optimal, because it is closest to the original Little et al method (I) while allowing sufficient space for maximum kernel spreading. ■

Individuals, organizations, and media are invited to quote or reprint articles or excerpts from articles in the IRRN. Duplicate prints of photos and illustrations are available to media on request from the Office of Information Services, IRRI. Persons who wish additional details of information presented in IRRN should write directly to the authors.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Varietal reaction to the kresek phase of bacterial blight

P. Ranga Reddy and Susanta K. Mohanty, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India

Bacterial blight of rice caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* exhibits two distinct types of symptoms: leaf blight and kresek or wilt. Leaf blight occurs in almost all of rice-growing India. Kresek is occasionally observed in experimental plots and in farmers' fields, particularly in isolated patches. Although kresek is more severe than leaf blight, information on it is limited. Therefore a study was initiated to artificially induce the disease and investigate the susceptibility of some popular rice varieties.

The roots of 15-day-old TN1 seedlings were washed thoroughly. The root tips were finely trimmed with scissors and dipped for 30 minutes in a 48-hour-old bacterial suspension (about 10⁹ cells/ml) grown on potato sucrose agar medium. The treated seedlings were transplanted in pots. Wilting symptoms began to appear 10 days after inoculation and continued appearing up to 20 days, by which time the maximum number of seedlings had collapsed. But not all the inoculated seedlings exhibited kresek; some surviving plants exhibited leaf blight symptoms. Bacteria reisolated from the wilted leaves were confirmed to be *X. oryzae* on the basis of physiological characters and

Reaction of some rice varieties to kresek. Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India.

Varieties	Wilted plants (%)
Lacrosse Zenith/Nira, Nagarbhog	0
BJ1, CO13, Krishna, Zukkoku, Sachikaze, Chinsurah Boro II, Raminad Str. 3, Kanto 51	2.0-8.5
TN1, Jamuna, Malagkit Sungsong, NP125, Cauvery, Kalinga I, Kalinga II, TKM6, Padma	10.0-18.5
IR8, Sigadis, Zenith, IR30, NC128I, Sona, Karuna, IR22, Katna, Kanchi, Rajeswari	22.0-38.5
Pusa 2-21, SLO 16, Jagannath, MTU 17, Supriya, IR24, Semora mangga, Pankaj, Sakti, Vijaya, Jaya	40.0-92.0

pathogenicity on rice plants.

Sixty-four indica and japonica varieties were inoculated using the above method. Ninety-two percent of the plants of the variety Jaya wilted, and 70% of Tadukan and Vijaya plants died. The varieties Lacrosse Zenith/Nira and Nagarbhog showed no wilting symptoms, indicating high kresek resistance. Wilting was minimal (2-6%) in BJ1, Chinsurah Boro II, Krishna, and Zukkoku. But TN1, which is highly susceptible to leaf blight, has only 12% wilting (see table). That indicates that the varietal reaction to the leaf blight phase is not similar to that to the kresek phase. ■

Resistance to sheath blight disease in India

S. Manian and K. Manibhushan Rao, Centre for Advanced Studies in Botany, University of Madras, Madras 600005, India

One hundred and thirty-four entries from the International Rice Sheath Blight Nursery (IRSHBN), 30 cultures from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) program, Hyderabad, and 6 entries from local collections were tested for resistance to sheath blight from March to July 1978 at the Maduravoil Field Research Laboratory, University of Madras, Madras, India. Checks were the resistant IR20, the moderately resistant IR1487-194-5-3-2, and the susceptible Pankaj. The inoculum was autoclaved rice stem cuttings (about 3–4 cm) with 5% dextrose, inoculated with a virulent isolate of *Corticium sasakii* and incubated for 15 days. Among the methods tried, the stem-tape inoculation technique was the most efficient for artificial inoculation. The sheaths of 90-day-old plants were inoculated 5 cm above the water level. They were scored for reaction 12 days later when the disease intensity was maximum in most cultivars.

The following entries were rated as highly resistant and resistant.

Highly resistant: BR4-30-51-2, BR51-49-6, IR2796-44-2, ARC 5925, and ARC 5943.